

A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE PREVALENCE OF OSTEOARTHRITIS AND ITS ASSOCIATION WITH CHOLESTROL LEVEL IN THE POPULATION OF PAKISTAN

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Abstract

Aim: Elevated cholesterol levels are a significant health concern, particularly regarding osteoarthritis. The primary objective of our study is to examine the prevalence of osteoarthritis, its association with elevated cholesterol levels, and other associated risk factors. The relationship between elevated cholesterol and the severity of osteoarthritis is not well understood.

Methods: A cross-sectional survey was conducted through face-to-face interviews in hospitals and clinics among 789 patients who underwent cholesterol testing. The main outcome variable was the cholesterol test, which was measured through blood tests. Statistical analyses were made using chi-square tests (significance at $p < 0.05$), correlation (significance at $p < 0.05$ and $p < 0.01$), and regression analysis.

Results: In our study, 43.3% were diagnosed with osteoarthritis. Among tested people, 43.3% had normal levels below 200 mg/dL, 24.9% were at risk, and 31.5% had elevated or dangerously high levels of cholesterol. Several factors showed significant association with elevated cholesterol level, such as age ($p=0.000$, $t=3.066$), gender ($p=0.001$), Education ($p=0.000$, $t=3.261$), Body mass index ($p=0.000$, $t=2.442$), sitting hours per day ($p=0.000$), meals per day ($p=0.000$), and many other as all have $p > 0.05$.

Conclusion: The findings indicate that many participants suffer from osteoarthritis, with a strong link to elevated cholesterol levels and lifestyle factors. This highlights the need to promote awareness about cholesterol management and healthy lifestyle choices for better osteoarthritis management.

INTRODUCTION

A lipid called cholesterol is essential for several bodily processes, including the synthesis of bile acids, vitamin D, and hormones (Tabas, 2002). Although cholesterol was first discovered in the 18th century, research on its connection to health did not start until the early 20th century (Steinberg, 2004). Cholesterol produced by the

liver influences fluidity and helps form cell membranes (Schade et al., 2020). Attached to lipoprotein particles, it moves through the blood and can be examined in a laboratory (Schade et al., 2020). Cholesterol has two kinds: high-density lipoprotein (HDL) (believed to have protective effect), and low-density lipoprotein

(LDL) (linked to increased inflammation and conditions like osteoarthritis) (Huff et al., 2017). Joint discomfort and inflammation are referred as arthritis (Schieir et al., 2017). Arthritis has many types that affect millions of peoples globally (Allen et al., 2022). Osteoarthritis (OA) is the most common type, characterized by the slow deterioration of cartilage, which increase joint stiffness and pain (Berenbaum, 2013). Osteoarthritis is divided into to further two types: primary OA (degenerative changes in the joints, mostly brought on by aging and wear and tear. It has no known underlying cause and is the most prevalent type of OA) (Lee et al., 2017) & secondary OA (Certain conditions like inflammatory arthritis, obesity, metabolic diseases (like diabetes), or previous joint injuries can cause secondary OA. Clinical evaluations and medical histories were used to identify the patients (Böhle et al., 2024). Diagnosis is primarily clinical, supported by radiography, with treatment options including acetaminophen, NSAIDs, and corticosteroid injections for flare-ups (Xie et al., 2019). Recent research has shown a connection between elevated cholesterol levels and OA (Farnaghi et al., 2017). Systemic inflammation, which worsens symptoms, can be exacerbated by LDL cholesterol (de Munter et al., 2016).

METHODOLOGY:

Study design:

The primary aim of the study is to investigate the relationship between cholesterol level and the presence of osteoarthritis (OA), including socioeconomic factors. A cross-sectional, observational (no treatments were applied) study was conducted using a modified questionnaire (Cho et al., 2021) of 29 questions that cover various aspects, including demographic information, medical history, lifestyle factors, socioeconomic status, laboratory tests, and clinical assessment. The study was conducted at DHQ Okara, Kasur, and THQ hospitals from December 2024 to March 2025, involving a total sample size of 789 individuals who underwent cholesterol testing at these facilities. Participants included both males and females who underwent random cholesterol testing and provided

informed consent; meanwhile, those with severe medical conditions were excluded.

Participants were recruited from these hospitals. Individuals who met the inclusion criteria were approached, and informed consent was provided. Each participant underwent a cholesterol test to measure their serum cholesterol levels and completed a questionnaire containing 29 questions via face-to-face interview. Results were documented for analysis. Participants were mainly divided into two groups: those diagnosed with OA and a control group without OA. To give a thorough picture of the variables affecting cholesterol levels in OA patients, both primary and secondary osteoarthritis (OA) were included. The cholesterol level of OA patients is compared. Additionally, lifestyle factors between the groups were analyzed to explore any correlation with cholesterol level. Appropriate tests were applied to check their significance. The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 2021 was used to analyze the collected data and form graphs from the questionnaire and the blood test results. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the demographics and clinical characteristics of the study population. The significance of variables was assessed using the chi-square test, correlation analysis (with significance levels of $p > 0.05$, $p > 0.01$), and regression analysis. If the significance level (p -value) was less than 0.05, the correlation seemed significant.

Blood sample collection:

Qualified staff at the hospital laboratory collected and processed blood samples for cholesterol testing by established protocols. In order to make sure that samples were handled properly, as the principal investigators, we depended on the laboratory's experience and standard operating procedures. The accuracy and dependability of the test results reported are guaranteed by the laboratory's accreditation and adherence to quality assurance procedures. We maintained the integrity of the research findings by ensuring that the data used in this study were produced using professional practices by acquiring the cholesterol reports from the hospital laboratory.

Criteria for OA diagnosis:

According to established clinical criteria that were in line with recommendations from the European League Against Rheumatism (EULAR) (<https://www.eular.org/eular-rheumafacts>) and the American College of Rheumatology (ACR) (<https://rheumatology.org/patients/osteoarthritis>), osteoarthritis (OA) was diagnosed in this study. Important elements included:

Clinical Symptoms:

Especially after extended use or periods of inactivity, patients complained of joint pain, stiffness, and swelling. To evaluate joint soreness, movement-induced crepitus, and swelling in the afflicted joints, a comprehensive examination was performed. X-rays were used to detect subchondral bone changes, osteophyte presence, and joint space narrowing, all of which are hallmarks of osteoarthritis.

A total of 789 participants with no age limit were enrolled in our study. Among these 342 (43.3%) reported as being diagnosed with OA, 447 (56.7%) had not. The results of the chi-square analysis show a statistically significant correlation between the diagnosis of arthritis and cholesterol levels, with ($p=0.000^*$, value=0.756). Regression analysis indicates higher cholesterol levels are linked with increased likelihood of OA diagnosis (coefficient = 0.189, $t = 3.771^{**}$) and (CI = 0.206 to 0.654). Additionally, a positive correlation result of 0.727^{**} indicated that as cholesterol levels increase, the health outcomes worsen for OA patients, as shown in Tables 1, 2 & 3. All things considered, these results highlight the crucial connection between high cholesterol and arthritis diagnosis. Data on family history of OA reveals a significant association ($p = 0.000^*$) and a negative correlation of 0.566^{**} . 467 (59.2%) did not report a family history of arthritis, whereas 322 (40.8%) did prove that genetics can worsen OA.

RESULTS

Serum cholesterol level in OA patients and controls: Analysis by clinical and laboratory data

Fig. 1 Comparison of pain levels in the control (without OA) & case (with OA) group

Further 43.3% (n=342) had total cholesterol levels below 200 mg/dL, 24.9% (n=197) had levels between

200 and 239 mg/dL (indicating risk), while 14.3% (n=113) had elevated cholesterol levels (240–259 mg/dL), and 17.2% (n=136) had dangerously high cholesterol levels (260 mg/dL and above).

Fig. 2 Difference in serum cholesterol level of OA patients

Demographic characteristics of patients with OA and controls

In age distribution the following age groups were used to group the participants: under 40 (n=226), 40–50 yrs (n=231), 50–60 yrs (n=215), and over 60 yrs (n=117). Significant relation in age, cholesterol, and OA was proved ($p=0.000^*$, value = 111.68) with positive correlation (0.321^{**}), as in Table 3. Further regression analysis in Table 2 shows cholesterol levels increase by 0.091 ($\beta = 0.091$, $p < 0.05$) for every year of higher age. Gender distribution showed 463 (58.7%) female participants and 326 (41.3%) male participants, showing a significant imbalance ($p = 0.001^*$) as in Table 1. Regression analysis indicates that gender predicts cholesterol level ($t = 1.502$), with a coefficient of 0.072, a standard error of 0.109, and with 95% CI (-0.050 and 0.378). Positive correlation association (0.104^{**}), coefficient 0.59 implies gender-based variation in cholesterol levels. Among the participants, 257 (32.6%) exercised weekly, 22 (2.8%) daily, 323 (40.9%) infrequently, and 187 (23.7%) never exercised. Significant association with (Chi square = 72.335, $p = 0.001^*$). Both regression ($t = -1.124$) and correlation coefficient of -0.809 ($r = -0.273^{**}$)

negative results show that more exercise is directly linked to lower cholesterol levels in Tables 1, 2 & 3. Occupation ($p = 0.024^*$) along with education reveals a significant association (p -value of 0.000^*) and ($t = 3.261^*$) with 95% CI. Among the participants, 43.5% (n=343) are working, whereas 56.5% (n=446) are either jobless or retired. Breakdown of education levels among the 789 respondents is as follows: Of the participants, 193 (24.5%) finished primary school, 330 (41.8%) finished secondary school, 249 (31.6%) advanced to higher secondary, and just 17 (2.2%) went on to higher secondary. Correlation results show a negative relationship with a coefficient of -0.151^{**} .

Association of lifestyle factors with cholesterol in OA patients and controls

Daily sitting hours results also shows significant association with (chi-square =155.376, $p = 0.000^*$) just 32 (4.1%) said they sat for fewer than five hours every day, 234 (29.7%) said they sat for 5-8 hrs., 50.3%, (n=397) reported sitting for 8-12 hrs., and 16.3% (n=126) said they sat for more than twelve hours. Both regression (95% CI, $t = 1.694$) and correlation ($r = 0.421^{**}$) reveal a

statistically significant (0.01*) positive relation between these two. Similarly, Body mass index (BMI) shows a significant association (Chi-square = 170.992, $p = 0.000^*$) with cholesterol and OA. BMI categories show that the majority, 39.3% (n=310), are in the 70–80 range, 34% in 80-90, 16% are greater than 90, and 10.6% (n=84) of people are below 70. Further supported by regression analysis ($t = 2.442^*$, $p = 0.036$), and positive correlation with (0.01* significance) $r =$

0.420**. Lastly meal frequency analysis, shows significance with ($p = 0.000^*$), and positive correlation by 95% CI with (coefficient = 0.188**). 2 people (0.3%) said they ate once a day, 312 (39.5%) ate twice a day, 434 (55%) ate three meals, and 41 (5.2%) ate more than three times a day. Reveals that increased meal frequency is linked to higher total caloric intake, and ultimately, to elevated cholesterol levels.

Table 4.1 Chi-Square Test Results: Cholesterol and Key Variables

Factors	Chi-square value	p-value
Cholesterol levels of the participant / Age of the participant	111.68	0.000*
Cholesterol levels of the participant / Gender of the participant	16.968	0.001*
Cholesterol levels of the participant / Marital status of the participant	57.320	0.000*
Cholesterol levels of the participant / Education level of the participant	39.460	0.000*
Cholesterol levels of the participants / Annual household income	15.511	0.078
Cholesterol levels of the participant / Occupation	9.458	0.024*
Cholesterol levels of the participant / Residential area	5.146	0.078
Cholesterol levels of the participant / How often do you check your cholesterol	7.415	0.161
Cholesterol levels of the participant / How often do you consume fast food	36.939	0.000*
Cholesterol levels of the participant / How often do you consume sugary drinks	11.319	0.255
Cholesterol levels of the participant / Consumption of fish (omega 3)	10/986	0.530
Cholesterol levels of the participant / Consumption of dairy products	15.080	0.089
Cholesterol levels of the participant / Consumption of ghee or butter	5.146	0.797
Cholesterol levels of the participant / Calcium supplements intake	12.877	0.045*
Cholesterol levels of the participant /Vitamin D supplement?	4.868	0.561
Cholesterol levels of the participant / Cholesterol-lowering medications?	333.375	0.000*
Cholesterol levels of the participant / Joint health supplements	217.960	0.000*
Cholesterol levels of the participant / How often do you perform exercise?	72.335	0.001*
Cholesterol levels of the participant / Your average hour of sitting per day?	155.376	0.000*
Cholesterol levels of the participant / Body Mass Index / BMI	170.992	0.000*
Cholesterol levels of the participant / Meals per day?	43.053	0.000*
Cholesterol levels of the participant /Have you experienced menopause?	103.232	0.000*
Cholesterol levels of the participant / Family history of arthritis?	259.136	0.000*
Cholesterol levels of the participant /Family history of cardiovascular?	146.379	0.000*
Cholesterol levels of the participant /Do you experience knee pain?	451.971	0.000*
Cholesterol levels of the participant / Knee pain limit your activities?	586.871	0.000*
Cholesterol levels of the participant / How often do you experience knee pain?	562.376	0.000*
Cholesterol levels of the participant / Have you been diagnosed with arthritis?	0.756	0.000*

*Significant result

Association of supplement intake with cholesterol level in OA patients

Calcium supplements (Chi-Square = 12.877, $p = 0.045^*$) show a significant association with OA.

Interestingly, 244 people (30.9%) take calcium supplements very infrequently, whereas 515 participants (65.3%) said they never take them. Sadly, none of the participants reported taking

calcium supplements every day, and only 30 (3.8%) said they did so once a week. In addition to calcium supplements, 34% (n=268) of the participants reported using cholesterol-lowering medications, while a significant majority, 66% (n=521), indicated that they do not. Both regression ($t = -3.075^{**}$) and correlation analysis ($r = -0.635^{**}$) showed a significant negative relationship ($r = -0.635^{**}$), indicating that more use of medication results in a lower cholesterol

level, and cholesterol-lowering medication ($p = 0.000^*$, Chi-Square = 333.375). Furthermore, regarding joint health, 26.4% (n=208) reported taking joint health supplements, and the majority, 73.6% (n=581), said they don't. Statistically significant association by (Chi-square = 217.960, $p = 0.000^*$) and ($t = -2.629^{**}$). A lower prevalence of osteoarthritis is associated with the use of joint health supplements, according to the 95% CI.

Table 4.2. Correlation analysis of cholesterol level and associated variables

Factors	Mean	Std. deviation	Correlation
Age of the participants	1.28	1.036	0.321**
Gender of the participant	0.59	0.493	0.104**
Marital status	1.16	0.510	0.242**
Occupation	0.57	0.496	0.073*
Education level of the participants	1.11	0.796	-0.151**
Annual household income	1.48	0.618	0.009
Residential Area	0.38	0.484	0.005
How often do you check your cholesterol level	2.76	0.457	-0.081*
Fast Food consumption	2.45	0.668	-0.037
Sugar drinks consumption	1.27	1.052	-0.069
Fish (omega 3) consumption	2.96	0.241	0.041
Dairy product consumption	1.26	0.977	-0.026
Ghee / Butter consumption	0.90	1.003	-0.036
Calcium supplement intake	2.61	0.560	0.002
Vitamin D supplements	0.66	0.515	-0.055
Cholesterol-lowering medications	0.74	0.474	-0.635**
Joint health supplements	1.86	0.441	-0.514**
How often you perform exercise	1.86	-0.809	-0.273**
Sitting hours per day	1.78	0.756	0.421**
Body mass index	1.55	0.882	0.420**
Meals per day	1.65	0.580	0.188**
Experience menopause	1.07	0.866	0.233**
Family history of arthritis	0.59	0.492	0.566**
Family history of cardiovascular	0.76	0.426	0.424**
Experience knee pain	0.53	0.499	0.701**
Knee pain and daily life activities	0.83	0.972	0.735**
How often do you experience knee pain	2.28	0.914	-0.715**
Diagnosed with arthritis?	0.57	0.496	0.727**

*Significant correlation at 0.05 level

**significant correlation at 0.01 level

Two significance levels were employed in the correlation analysis: 0.01 and 0.05. Strong correlations that are unlikely to happen by accident are shown at the 0.01 level, whilst moderate significance is indicated at the 0.05 level.

Table 4.3. Regression analysis of cholesterol level and associated variables

Factors	Coefficient (β)	Std. Error	t-value	p-value	95% CI (lower & upper)
Age of the participants	0.091	0.032	3.066*	0.02	(0.036 , 0.162)
Gender of the participants	0.072	0.109	1.502	0.133	(-0.050 , 0.378)
Marital status	0.003	0.063	0.094	0.925	(-0.118, 0.130)
Occupation	-0.045	0.066	-1.529	0.127	(-0.231, 0.029)
Education of participant	0.092	0.040	3.261*	0.001	(0.052, 0.209)
Household income	-0.007	0.045	-0.275	0.783	(-0.100, 0.075)
Residential area	-0.023	0.055	-0.989	0.323	(-0.162, 0.053)
How often check your cholesterol	-0.025	0.056	-1.087	0.277	(-0.171, 0.049)
Fast food consumption	-0.049	0.042	-1.961	0.50	(-0.164, -0.000)
Sugary drinks consumption	0.026	0.026	1.045	0.296	(-0.024, 0.079)
Fish (omega 3) consumption	0.040	0.102	1.847	0.065	(-0.012, 0.389)
Dairy products consumption	-0.008	0.026	-0.350	0.726	(-0.060, 0.042)
Ghee & butter consumption	0.012	0.025	0.561	0.575	(-0.035, 0.062)
Calcium supplements intake	0.023	0.047	0.976	0.330	(-0.046, 0.138)
Vitamin D supplements	0.008	0.048	0.362	0.718	(-0.077, 0.112)
Cholesterol lowering medications	-0.105	0.081	-3.075**	0.002	(-0.410 , 0.090)
Joint health supplements	-0.083	0.080	-2.629**	0.009	(-0.370 -0.054)
How often you perform exercise	-0.028	0.034	-1.124	0.262	(-0.105, 0.029)
Sitting hours per day	0.048	0.042	1.694	0.091	(-0.011, 0.155)
Body mass index	0.070	0.036	2.442*	0.015	(0.017 , 0.160)
Meals per day	-0.014	0.044	-0.631	0.528	(-0.115, 0.059)
Have you experience menopause	-0.065	0.063	-1.332	0.183	(-0.209, 0.040)
Family history of arthritis	-0.035	0.071	-1.113	0.266	(-0.219, 0.060)
Family history of cardiovascular	-0.086	0.065	-3.482**	0.001	(-0.354, -0.099)
Do you experience knee pain	-0.092	0.115	-1.814	0.070	(0.433, 0.017)
Knee pain affect daily life activities	0.156	0.063	2.862*	0.004	(0.057, 0.305)
How often experience knee pain	-0.140	0.059	-2.919	0.004	(-0.288, -0.057)
diagnosed with arthritis ?	-0.189	0.114	-3.771**	0.000	(-0.654, -0.206)

1. *Positive significant relation
2. **negative significant relationship

Knee pain, an indicator of OA, shows a significant association ($p = 0.000^*$) with a correlation of (-0.701^{**}) . 46.6% ($n=368$) of people responded that they experience knee pain, and 53.3% ($n=421$) said they don't. The frequency of knee discomfort and cholesterol levels is strongly correlated ($\chi^2 = 562.376$, $p = 0.000^*$), further supported by correlation (0.735^{**}) . 54% (426 people) of the 789 participants said they had knee pain occasionally,

compared to 25% (197) who reported it monthly, 15.7% (124) who reported it weekly, and 5.3% (42) who reported it daily. Strong positive correlation (0.715^{**}) and ($p = 0.000^*$, $\chi^2 = 562.376$) proved the effect of elevated cholesterol levels and daily life activities. Results of residential area, annual household income ($p = 0.078$), sugary drinks ($p = 0.255$), fish consumption ($p = 0.530$), dairy product consumption ($p = 0.089$), and consumption of

ghee and butter ($p = 0.797$) don't show any significant association with cholesterol and OA.

Discussion:

The study delved into the relationship between cholesterol levels and lifestyle factors in OA patients. Results emphasize a clear association between elevated cholesterol and OA. Given the growing acknowledgment of the impact of elevated cholesterol in OA patients, these findings hold substantial importance.

In our study, increased age, BMI, more meal intake, sedentary behavior, no regular exercise, and elevated cholesterol level were identified as contributing factors ($p < 0.05$). Similar findings have also been reported in the literature, reflecting the importance of managing BMI & cholesterol, managing caloric intake, reducing sedentary behavior, and regular exercise (Schwager et al., 2022). Higher total caloric intake by eating more frequently results in consuming more saturated fats that raise cholesterol, which could be the cause of this (Thomas et al., 2018). In many parts of Pakistan, fish (omega-3) is not a staple food; regional availability and cultural preferences have a significant impact on eating habits. Total intake of omega-3 fatty acids, which are good for controlling cholesterol, may be impacted by this restricted intake. Pakistani dietary habits are primarily meat-based, which may outweigh the possible advantages of eating fish (Hanif et al., 2022). Weight gain, stiffness, and joint discomfort are all consequences of a sedentary lifestyle that might increase the risk of osteoarthritis (Wang et al., 2023). Given that many participants had elevated BMIs, it is imperative to concentrate on focused interventions that promote physical activity and weight management. Additionally, we found that there was a significant gender difference in cholesterol levels, with females exhibiting significantly higher levels than males. This emphasizes the necessity of customized strategies to successfully handle these variances (Papathanasiou et al., 2021). This result highlights how crucial it is to take gender into account when examining the study population's

cholesterol levels. Insufficient consumption of necessary supplements worsens joint issues because it is necessary for preserving bone strength and density (Thomas et al., 2018). There are several reasons why people are afraid to use supplements. For example, people may be unaware of the advantages and disadvantages of supplements due to inadequate health education. Furthermore, many people are unable to receive the necessary guidance due to limited access to healthcare. People may find it more difficult to get the proper medical care due to socioeconomic difficulties.

It is impossible to overestimate the role that education plays in resolving these problems. We can enable people to make knowledgeable decisions about their health by putting in place educational programs that emphasize health literacy. People can take proactive measures toward healthier lives when they know how to manage conditions like high cholesterol and osteoarthritis. In the end, expanding educational opportunities can benefit everyone's health (Schwager et al., 2022). According to our data, osteoarthritis was most frequently found in the knees (Primorac et al., 2020), with a few cases found in the hips and hands (Katz et al., 2021). Due to their frequent use and weight bearing during daily activities, these joints are frequently impacted (Vincent & Watt, 2022). We identified two major factors high cholesterol and a sedentary lifestyle that can be especially harmful to knee health. The significance of customized management approaches for people with osteoarthritis (OA) is highlighted by this finding. Many people find that altering their daily routines has a big impact on their wellbeing. Better results can be obtained by promoting physical activity and movement as well as a healthy diet to reduce cholesterol. We can assist patients in better managing their OA and enhancing their general quality of life by addressing these lifestyle choices. The goal is to enable people to take control of their health by implementing minor adjustments that, over time, may result in significant gains.

Conclusion:

According to our research, lifestyle choices have a significant impact on osteoarthritis (OA) and cholesterol levels. These results highlight the importance of taking cholesterol into account when treating and keeping an eye on OA patients. In conclusion, our research supports the notion that lifestyle factors contribute to OA and that high cholesterol is associated with it.

Controlling cholesterol levels is essential when doing clinical evaluations for OA. We should educate people about healthy lifestyle choices, promote physical activity, and increase awareness of how diet affects joint health. We can lessen the prevalence of OA and enhance general wellbeing by addressing these factors.

Our study group's smaller size might limit how broadly our results can be applied to the broader population. Furthermore, the findings may only apply to the particular population and healthcare environments that we examined. There's a chance that some errors could have affected our findings because we used self-reported data.

List of Abbreviations

OA	Osteoarthritis
BMI	Body mass index
HDL	High density lipoprotein
LDL	Low-density lipoprotein
NSAID	non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs
SPSS	Statistical package for the social sciences
CI	Confidence interval

Declarations

Ethics approval and consent to participate

Permission was obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee, the department head, DHQ Hospital, Okara, Kasur, and THQ Hospitals. A consent form was filled out by each participant after the purpose of the study was explained.

Consent for publication

All participants were informed that their data would be used solely for research purposes, and they were assured of full confidentiality.

Availability of data and materials

The data gathered, used, and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

Competing interests

Maiha Ghaffar, Anam Abbas, Samavia Mustafa, Atifa Waheed, Sana Khan and Razia Bibi declare that they have no competing interests.

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Author Contributions

Maliha Ghaffar: conception or design of the work & revising it critically, Anam Abbas: carried out the studies, collected the data, drafted the manuscript, and performed the statistical analysis under the supervision of Maliha Ghaffar. Samavia Mustafa, Atifa Waheed, Sana Khan, Rabia Yaseen, and Razia Bibi participated in the acquisition, analysis, and interpretation of the data. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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